

Number of insects /10 sweeps

Field populations of 2 grain sucking bugs in irrigated and upland rice, in relation to crop phenology.

was slightly higher than that of *Stenocoris*. In upland rice, *Aspavia* was the predominant species through all growth stages. □

Systemic and foliar applications of neem seed bitters (NSB) to control green leafhopper (GLH) and rice tungro virus (RTV) disease

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In laboratory and greenhouse trials, NSB applied systemically or as a foliar spray has been found effective against GLH and RTV and was safe to rice pest predators. In 1987 wet season, we tested

Yield; populations of GLH, predatory mirid, and spiders; and RTV infection in field plots planted to RTV-susceptible IR42 treated with neem seed bitters (NSB) or insecticide.^a IRRI, 1987 wet season.

Treatment	GLH (no.) /20 hills			Mirid and spiders (no.)/20 hills			RTV infection (%)			Yield (t/ha)
	50 DT	60 DT	70 DT	50 DT	60 DT	70 DT	25 DT	45 DT	65 DT	
NSB 5,000 ppm (systemic)	16 b	19 b	17 b	22 a	24 a	33 a	1 a	15 a	27 a	2.8 b
NSB systemic + NSB 10,000 ppm sprayed fortnightly	11 a	13 b	13 b	22 a	25 a	31 a	2 ab	13 a	25 a	3.3 ab
NSB systemic + NSB 10,000 ppm sprayed weekly	10 a	15 b	18 b	23 a	23 a	31 a	1 a	13 a	23 a	3.2 ab
Monocrotophos (0.75 kg ai/ha) sprayed weekly	10 a	4 a	3 a	7 b	9 b	13 b	2 ab	12 a	16 a	3.6 a
Citowett (250 ppm) – water solution (control) sprayed weekly	15 b	21 b	14 b	25 a	28 a	39 a	3 b	24 b	37 b	2.7 b

^a Av of 4 replications. Separation of means in a column by DMRT at the 5% level.

its efficacy on GLH- and RTV-susceptible IR42 rice planted at IRRI.

Two application methods were used: 1) Roots of 21-d-old seedlings were soaked in a 5,000 ppm NSB solution for 12 h before transplanting, and 2) systemically treated seedlings were sprayed with 10,000 ppm NSB solution (emulsified with 250 ppm Citowett) at 1-wk (8 times) or 2-wk (4 times) intervals beginning 5 d after transplanting (DT). In control plots, untreated seedlings were sprayed with monocrotophos (0.75 kg ai/ ha) or water with 250 ppm Citowett at 1-wk intervals beginning 5 DT. All sprays were applied at 8 liters/ ha, using an ultralow volume applicator. Treatments were in 40-m² plots with 4 replications.

Field, populations of GLH nymphs and adults and the predators mirid

Cyrtorhinus lividipennis and spiders were recorded visually 50, 60, and 70 DT on 20 randomly selected hills/plot. Percent RTV infection in hills in each plot (excluding border rows), based on visual symptoms of yellowing and stunting in infected plants, was recorded 25, 45, and 65 DT.

GLH population at 50 DT was significantly lower in NSB- or insecticide-sprayed plots (see table). By 60 and 70 DT, the pest population had decreased in insecticide-treated plots. Populations of the predatory mirid and spiders decreased more in insecticide-treated plots than in neem or control plots.

RTV infection at 45 and 65 DT was significantly lower in insecticide- and neem-treated plots than in control plots. □

Farm machinery

Low-cost treadle pump for supplementary irrigation of rainfed farms

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We developed four low-cost treadle pump models in cooperation with the IRRI Agricultural Engineering Department, Philippines. The pumps are designed to lift water from tubewells, dug wells, or creeks for supplementary irrigation of upland crops after wet season rice.

Portable models MA05 and MA06 utilized the pump housing, cylinder liners, and valves of locally available